

THE INFLUENCE OF THE ECOLOGICAL ENVIRONMENT ON THE BODY OF WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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Abstract. *Reproductive Health indicates that people have a responsible, satisfying, healthy reproductive system and have a safer sex life and that they have the ability to reproduce and the freedom to make decisions if so, when and for how long. One interpretation of this implies that men and women must be informed of having access to safe, effective, affordable, and acceptable methods of birth control; access to related health services of sexual, reproductive medicine to implement health education programs to emphasize the importance of women by going safely to pregnancy and childbirth can provide couples with the best opportunity to have a healthy baby.*

Keywords: *female, reproductive, age, health, environment, ecology, risk, environmental factor, environment.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СРЕДЫ НА ОРГАНИЗМ ЖЕНЩИН РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. *Репродуктивное здоровье указывает на то, что у людей есть ответственная, удовлетворительная, здоровая репродуктивная система и более безопасная сексуальная жизнь, а также что они имеют возможность размножаться и свободу принимать решения, если да, то когда и как долго. Одна интерпретация этого подразумевает, что мужчины и женщины должны быть проинформированы о наличии доступа к безопасным, эффективным, доступным и приемлемым методам контроля над рождаемостью; доступ к сопутствующим медицинским услугам в области сексуальной и репродуктивной медицины для реализации программ санитарного просвещения, чтобы подчеркнуть важность женщин путем безопасного перехода к беременности и родам, может предоставить парам наилучшие возможности для рождения здорового ребенка.*

Ключевые слова: *женский пол, репродуктивный возраст, здоровье, окружающая среда, экология, риск, экологический фактор, окружающая среда.*

INTRODUCTION

Women face inequalities in reproductive health care. Inequalities vary according to the socio-economic situation, the level of education, age, nationality, religion and the resources present in their environment. For example, low-income individuals may lack the resources to provide appropriate medical services and knowledge to find out what is needed to maintain reproductive health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Environmental factors are a set of certain conditions and elements of the environment that have a specific impact on the functioning of organisms. Environmental factors are divided into 2 large groups — abiotic factors and biotic factors. In ecology, there is also the concept of "limiting factors", the composition of which can include any factor limiting the existence and development of organisms. Any fragments of the environment that affect living organisms are called environmental factors. Environment-consists of land, water, air and underground parts. In addition to the concept of the external environment, there is also the concept of living conditions,

which includes light, heat, water, nutrition, among other elements or factors necessary for the survival of the organism. In 1933, D.N.Kashkarov divides environmental factors into 3 groups. Later in 1950, Alyokhin proposes to study environmental factors by dividing them into climatic, edaphical, orographic, biotic, anthropogenic and historical groups. Environmental factors are divided into 3 main groups:

1. Abiotic factors are the sum of the conditions of an inorganic nature or a dead nature. These include temperature, light, humidity, water, soil, relief.
2. Biotic factors: this includes elements of living nature (the influence of living organisms on each other and on the habitat). Biotic factors are divided into phyto'genic and zoo genic factors. Phyto'genic factors mean the influence of high and deep plants on the body, while zoo genic factors mean the influence of all animals on the body.
3. Anthropogenic factors-this is due to human activity

RESULTS

And the result of the influence of these factors on certain organisms is diverse. The most favorable level of the factor for the life of the organism is called the optimal level. The highest level of any environmental factors is the maximum, and the lowest level is the minimum. Naturally, for each living organism, one or another environmental factor will have its own maximum, minimum and optimum. The house fly can live from 7° to 0°. The optimum level of living for them is 36-40°. It should be noted that only when environmental factors have a complex effect on organisms, they give a high result.

According to the definition of the World Health Organization, the reproductive health of the population is the psychological, social and physiological readiness of the individual to create a family and continue the family. The term includes sexual health, the absence of sexually transmitted diseases and other factors that can negatively affect Pregnancy, pregnancy, the mental and physical health of the child. In recent years, the younger generation has led an unhealthy lifestyle, which negatively affects reproductive health. The main indicator of reproductive health is a successful pregnancy and childbirth. To assess reproductive health, there are the following criteria:

1. the state of the mother's body, the presence of pathologies of various nature, general immunity;
2. father's health (50% of the successful result depends on the state of the male body, its chronic pathologies);
3. hereditary diseases;
4. STI (sexually transmitted infections);
5. HIV/AIDS (human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immunodeficiency syndrome);
6. low abortion and infant mortality;
7. infertility reduction;
8. the number of women using contraceptives.

In recent years, research has been actively carried out to study the influence of causes of various nature on the reproductive health of a woman. These risk factors include the following groups:

1. Socio - psychological-includes the presence in a tense economic environment (material well-being), stress, anxiety and fear.

2. Occupational exposure to harmful or hazardous substances should be excluded even before pregnancy, when conditions can affect labor activity, normal functioning of organs.
3. genetic causes.
4. environmental factors.

DISCUSSION

The latest technologies greatly facilitate human life, help fight serious diseases, but at the same time contribute to the emergence of new ones. The destruction of the ozone layer of the atmosphere leads to an increase in the amount of ultraviolet radiation that falls on the surface of the planet, which negatively affects the state of the general immunity of the population. In addition, the so-called global warming gradually leads to a change in temperature regimes on the planet, which, together with electromagnetic radiation, negatively affects the reproductive health of a person. The pace of life and the level of urbanization of modern society lead to increased stress, especially in large cities. Everyday life, nervous overload, depression. In addition, in recent decades there has been a significant increase in car accidents, which often lead to injuries that directly affect a person's reproductive health. There are a number of drugs that negatively affect reproductive health due to hormonal disorders. In addition, there are a number of pathologies that affect the state of reproductive health of a man and a woman. Such diseases include the following deviations:

1. Increasing the spread of sexually transmitted infections often leads to irreversible disorders of the genitourinary system.
2. Cardiovascular pathologies affect the general condition of the body, limiting physiological capabilities.
3. Some infectious diseases (for example, chickenpox, mumps) are the causes of infertility, especially in boys.
4. Diabetes mellitu's, liver and kidney pathologies can lead to hormonal disruptions.
5. In many cases, congenital diseases are initially the causes of reproductive problems.

The concept of reproductive health includes various activities, services, methods aimed at maintaining reproductive function at the proper level even in unfavorable environmental conditions. There are the following preventive measures:

1. prevention of sexually transmitted diseases;
2. prevention of serious pathologies affecting the genital area;
3. education of the older population and adolescents on topical issues for a particular generation;
4. preventive measures to prevent abortion (especially at an early age).

One of the most acute problems of modern society has become the problem of teenage children who are most susceptible to the social negative impact of society and the environment. In addition, a number of studies indicate a special sensitivity of the reproductive system of adolescents to their influence. The formation, development and formation of the reproductive system begins from conception and continues until puberty, i.e. Up to 18 years old. The implementation of the function of the female reproductive system (PC) is associated with the age of 18-44 years. Human reproductive health is determined by biological, social and economic factors, including ecology, the quality of medical care and the complex influence of the individual's lifestyle. Lisicin (1989) calculated that the most important indicators of human health, including 50% with reproductive health conditions and lifestyle, 20-25% with the state of the external environment, 20% with hereditary and hereditary factors; and only 10-15% with the

quality of medical care. However, this information is only valid for adults. G.Dubovoy (2002) explains that 50% of adult health indicators depend on the living environment, 33% - on the state of the population, 10% - on the level of development of Health and 4% - on the standard of living of the population. At the same time, the importance of the listed factors for children is slightly different and is estimated at 31%; 43.2%; 12.2% and 13.6%. Each of the above factors has its own age-specific significance and changes its rating throughout life.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, biological factors are especially important for a woman - hereditary, maternal health, the process of pregnancy and childbirth, as well as the quality and availability of medical care, especially in the first 2 years of life. Due to the totality of the influence of environmental and socio-economic factors, an alarming situation has developed in recent decades, which has led to a significant deterioration in the state of Public Health, a decrease in fertility and fertility. The latest technologies greatly facilitate human life, help fight serious diseases, but at the same time contribute to the emergence of new ones. The destruction of the ozone layer of the atmosphere leads to an increase in the amount of ultraviolet radiation that falls on the surface of the planet, which negatively affects the state of the general immunity of the population. In addition, the so-called global warming gradually leads to a change in temperature regimes on the planet, which, together with electromagnetic radiation, negatively affects the reproductive health of a person.

REFERENCES

1. Rustamova, R. P. (2022). THE ROLE OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INDIVIDUAL. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(NUU Conference 2), 898-903.
2. Parpievna, R. R. (2022). ACTUALITY AND DIRECTIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG STUDENTS. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 2(3), 139-146.
3. Parpievna, R. R., & Zafarovich, O. R. (2021). Application of Artificial Neural Networks for Analysis of Pathologies in Blood Vessels. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 4074-4082.
4. Ravshan, O., Ra'no, R., Usmon, A., Risbek, S., & Azizkhon, K. (2020). The aral tragedy and its threats to regional life, issues of cooperation in solving the aral problem. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(4), 3016-3021.
5. Tukhtaeva, K., Karaeva, K., Saidova, S., Ibragimova, Z., & Djuraeva, M. (2020). MAIN PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING EFL IN MIXED-ABILITY GROUPS.
6. Karaeva, K., Tukhtaeva, K., Ibragimova, Z., Djuraeva, M., & Saidova, S. (2020). Main peculiarities of teaching efl in mixed-ability groups. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(5), 1712-1715.
7. Tukhtaeva, K. DIVERSE OPINIONS ABOUT MODERN CASE SYSTEM IN THE ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES.
8. Komilova, N. (2022). GENDERED LEXICON OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 192-194.
9. Sotvoldiyevna, U. D. (2022). Political Euphemisms in English and Uzbek Languages (A Comparative Analysis). *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 9, 92-96.

10. Satvoldievna, U. D. (2021). Axiological Characteristics Of English, Uzbek And Russian Phraseological Units. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(06), 40-45.
11. https://www.sammu.uz/uz/pages/journal_reproductive_health
12. <https://xs.uz/uz/post/fuqarolarning-reproduktiv-salomatligini-saqlash-togrisida>
13. <https://fayllar.org/sana-11-mavzu-reproduktiv-salomatlikning-ijtimoiy-psixologik-x.html>